

CHARACTERIZATION AND NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION OF AN RTM CURE PROCESS WITH CFRP MOLDS AND INDEPENDENT HEAT PATCHES

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ABSTRACT

The knowledge of the temperature development within thick carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) parts during cure is crucial for the production of high performance aerospace components given that high exothermic temperature peaks may degrade material properties and introduce additional components of residual stress. During cure of CFRP parts with complex geometry and varying cross sections a uniform temperature distribution and hence homogenous material property development is sought.

A novel resin transfer molding (RTM) tooling concept, consisting of CFRP mold parts with integrated in situ heating patches, is modelled within a commercial finite element platform (Abaqus) for further cure simulation utilizing Compro/CCA. A mono-component resin system and the tooling material were characterized by means of differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and NanoFlash™ tests. Characterized material data was verified by simulative prediction and experimental comparison of a 30 mm laminate coupon during cure. A simulation strategy was developed and implemented to model the transient thermal response of the in situ heating device by modification of boundary conditions via a feedback control system. Finally a typical process temperature cycle has been used to validate the implemented simulation strategy numerically.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Context and Background

The potentially high integral structures of carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) parts produced by the resin transfer molding (RTM) process leads to various challenges in the production process. The polymerization rate depends on temperature and degree of cure; the degree of polymerization should be as homogeneous as possible to impede residual stress build up during manufacturing. Given that exothermic cure energy increases laminate temperature, parts with varying cross sections may require non-uniform tool temperatures within the cavity for a more homogeneous cure in reasonable amounts of time.

Other challenges are the cost- and energy efficiency in tool manufacturing and service life as well as the thermal expansion discrepancy between metallic tool and CFRP part. The handling and production of large metallic tools requires large machinery and is expensive. Due to higher coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) the metallic tool shrinks onto the part with low CTE during cool-down. Hence new tooling concepts with CFRP tool material were introduced for flat and hat type shaped molds [1].

For large, thick and highly integral parts such as e.g. helicopter rotor blades, all the above mentioned challenges apply. Standard RTM tools may not lead to desired results, as the laminate thickness in concerning parts changes from approximately 30mm in the monolithic section to 1mm in the sandwich section and a temperature cycle applied globally on the part would lead to different cure stages in the sections throughout the processing time. With the rotor blades' dimension in radial direction being in the range of 3 m to 6 m, the corresponding metallic tool requires high energy and financial resources for production and service life due to high thermal masses.

To address these challenges the collaborating tool manufacturer Qpoint developed a new tooling concept consisting of CFRP molds in shell construction and in situ heating patches, which are

controlled independently [2]. The combination of this heating system with the low thermal mass and conductivity of the tool material lead to the capability of heat introduction where and when it is needed and thus opens up the potential to an optimized, more homogeneous cure. However, lower thermal tool conductivity of CFRP compared to metal alloys, particularly in the through thickness direction, leads to a higher risk of exothermic temperature overshoot during cure and in worst case material degradation. In-depth process comprehension for the application at hand, especially of the cure behavior and temperature development, enables a full utilization of the potential of such a tool concept.

Process simulation is a powerful tool to understand and predict the temperature development during cure and to optimize the applied cure cycle. The computationally efficient investigation of temperature and degree of cure distributions of thick CFRP parts led to the development of several one-dimensional finite difference schemes. To account for more complex geometries within autoclave processing two- [3, 4] and three-dimensional finite element process simulation codes [5] have been set up. These simulation approaches were successfully applied on RTM processing, too [6, 7]. The simulated tool materials for RTM processes were mostly aluminum and steel in accordance to the applications. These tool materials are typically used to account for good machinability and homogeneous heat introduction due to high thermal mass and conductivity. In some cases, where dimensional fidelity during the temperature ramp were of high concern, invar was used [8].

1.2 Objectives and Structure

This work aims to set the foundation for the cure simulation of a generic rotor blade manufactured with the novel self-heated tool concept. The capability of an accurate curing simulation with an in situ heating patch tool is developed.

First, materials characterization have been conducted to capture the cure behavior of the investigated resin system. Thermal properties of the tooling material have been tested. Validation was accomplished on coupon level. Furthermore a simulation strategy has been set up to implement a temperature controlled heat patch device in the cure simulation via Abaqus COMPRO/ Common Component Architecture (CCA) platform [5]. Finally validation of the simulation strategy has been accomplished by cure simulation of the thermal response of a 30 mm thick CFRP laminate.

2. MATERIAL CHARACTERIZATION

Two different CFRP material systems and their material properties were required for the investigation: Only the thermal material properties in fully cured state as a function of temperature are relevant for the tool material. In contrast, the material properties for the part are required as a function of degree of polymerization and temperature. To the author's knowledge, no cure characterization of the resin system CYCOM 823-1 RTM from Cytec is available from literature. Hence characterization of the thermochemical properties were necessary. The laminate properties were estimated subsequently with micromechanical models and fiber properties from literature.

2.1 Cure kinetics

The investigated resin system CYCOM 823-1 RTM is an anhydride epoxy resin system from Cytec. The degree of cure is defined as the ratio of the time integral of the specific released heat flow $\dot{q}(t)$ to the total amount of releasable heat H_r in the resin.

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{H_r} \int \dot{q}(t) dt \quad (1)$$

Hence, the time derivative of equation 1, the cure rate $\dot{\alpha}$ defines the change in material properties and the amount of released polymerization energy in time during processing. The cure rate is dependent on the degree of cure and temperature.

A series of dynamic and isothermal DSC runs were conducted to find an expression for the cure rate of the resin studied. The overall objective of the work was the investigation of the thermal management of the production of thick CFRP laminates produced with CFRP tools. Due to low tool conductivity and thermal mass a potential risk of occurring exothermic peaks were suspected. Hence

the cure kinetic model was required to give an accurate description over a large range of temperatures above the cure temperature of 125 °C, which is the final temperature hold according to the manufacturer's recommended cure cycle. The ultimate heat of reaction was determined on a total of 11 dynamic runs at three different temperature rates of 1.5 °C/min, 3 °C/min and 5 °C/min. Utilizing a linear baseline, the ultimate heat of reaction H_r was determined to be 352.4 J/g on average with a standard deviation of 11.6 J/g. The uncured midpoint glass transition temperature T_{g0} was measured at -47.8 °C with a standard deviation of 1.2 °C. The glass transition temperature $T_{g\infty}$ of fully cured resin was determined in a similar manner on nine experiments, the resulting mean value was 106.7 °C with a standard deviation of 4.2 °C.

Isothermal runs were conducted and used as an input for the cure rate model fit. The isothermal heat flow after complete cure has been extrapolated to represent the isothermal baseline for calculation of the time dependent specific released heat flow $\dot{q}(t)$. The experimental temperatures chosen for the isothermal DSC runs were set at 80 °C, 90 °C, 100 °C, 110 °C, 125 °C, 140 °C and 160 °C. At 80 °C no significant cure could be detected within a reasonable amount of time, hence the experimental values were not considered meaningful for the modelling. The evolution of the degree of cure for the isothermal holds at different temperature are shown in Figure 1. All experiments reached full cure at the temperatures investigated. This fact is attributed to the low ultimate glass transition temperature of 106.7°C. Even the lowest temperature of 90°C is close enough to reach full cure after ~1day cure time.

Figure 1: Evolution of the degree of cure at isothermal temperatures

Literature cure kinetic models with the ability to describe two different chemical reactions were fitted to experimental data with means of a weighted nonlinear least square regression analysis. The model “CK9” from Convergent led to a satisfactory fit over the whole contemplated temperature range, which is shown in Figure 1 [5].

Cure rate models with modelling of diffusion behavior, such as CK9, require consideration of the free volume and typically utilize the DiBenedetto equation for the evolution of glass transition temperature with the degree of cure [9]:

$$T_g(\alpha) = T_{g0} + \frac{\alpha\lambda(T_{g\infty} - T_{g0})}{1 - (1 - \lambda)\alpha} \quad (2)$$

To determine the model constant, additional dynamic scanning calorimetry (DSC) runs were conducted. A series of specimens have been partially cured isothermally at 125 °C within the DSC. Subsequently to the cool-down, dynamic runs were applied to measure the residual enthalpy to capture

the evolution of the glass transition temperature with the degree of cure in-between T_{g0} and $T_{g\infty}$. Two specimens have been prepared in a similar way at 100 °C to gain additional data points close to full cure. The resulting experimental determination of the evolution of glass transition temperature with degree of cure is shown in Figure 2. The DiBenedetto constant λ was fitted with assistance of a least square regression analysis to the experimental data.

Figure 2: Evolution of glass transition temperature with degree of cure and DiBenedetto approximation

2.2 Evolution of heat capacity and conductivity with temperature and cure

The heat capacity of the curing resin was measured by dynamic modulated DSC (MDSC) runs with a temperature ramp of 3 °C/min.

Five specimen were tested with two successive MDSC runs: The first run was conducted to measure the uncured heat capacity over temperature up to the start of reaction. The second run was conducted with the cured specimens to obtain data on the heat capacity over temperature in the glassy and rubbery state above glass transition temperature. The mean progression of the specific heat capacity with temperature for uncured and cured state of all specimens is shown in Figure 3.

Neglecting the initial deviations until the heat flow is stabilized, a good agreement with maximal standard deviations of 37 J/kg/°C, 23 J/kg/°C and 32 J/kg/°C for the regions uncured, cured glassy and cured rubbery of the five specimens were reached. A material model with dependencies of temperature and degree of cure was fitted to the experimental data via least square regression analysis. Almost no discrepancy between model and mean measurement data was identified if the initial settling period is neglected, as shown in Figure 3.

Temperature conductivity of the cured resin was measured by means of the NanoFlash™-method at five different temperatures with three specimens each. To calculate the heat conductivity the temperature conductivity has to be multiplied with the density and heat capacity. Measurement of the former provided the value of 1228.8 kg/m³, the latter has been determined with the DSC as described above. The resulting heat conductivity at the measured temperatures is shown in Table 1. A material model with linear dependencies on the degree of cure and temperature has been fitted to the data with least square regression analysis.

Figure 3: Mean experimental specific heat capacity and material model approximation, left side: uncured resin, right side: cured resin

Temperature [°C]	Temp. cond. [mm ² /s]	Std. dev. [mm ² /s]	Heat cond. [W/m/°C]
20	0.116	0.003	0.153
50	0.108	0.001	0.160
80	0.100	0.001	0.164
130	0.079	0.001	0.180
150	0.077	0.001	0.180

Table 1: Resin heat conductivity resulting from measurement

.2.3 Material characterization validation

The material characterization of the curing resin was made over a wide temperature range to ensure the capability of the material models of representing significant exothermic reactions as well as cure below the final glass transition temperature $T_{g\infty}$. Thus, for validation of the material models a coupon layout where a significant exothermal peak is expected to occur was set up. A 145x145x31 mm laminate coupon with 120 layers of +45° non-crimp fabric (NCF), made of Toho Tenax HTS40 fibers, was manufactured with vacuum bag technique on a self-heated CFRP plate. The fiber data was extracted from literature [10, 11]. The resulting fiber volume fraction was 54.4 %. On the top side, another self-heated CFRP plate was positioned to introduce heat from both sides. The remaining sides were insulated to obtain nearly adiabatic boundaries.

Given that the foil and breather material influence conductivity and neat resin regions at the inlet influence thermal behavior, considerable modelling effort was undertaken to ensure an accurate validation. In order to be able to detect the effect of inaccuracies in the model a relatively high number of 18 thermocouples were placed within the laminate in three planes, 12 thermocouples on top and bottom of the laminate and six in the center plane. The top and bottom thermocouple temperatures were used as input for the temperature boundary condition in the simulation and positioned accordingly. The measured temperatures over time were interpolated in space for each time step and the resulting temperature field at the top and bottom side of the laminate were read in as temperature boundary conditions at the top and bottom nodes during the cure simulation. The starting temperature field was interpolated and applied in a similar way. Validation was made by comparison of the thermocouple temperatures in the center plane of the laminate with simulated data. The thermocouple in-plane positioning on the center plane implied four thermocouple locations on each side with 10 mm distance to the laminate edges and two thermocouples next to each other in the center to accurately capture temperatures in the assumed region with the least impact of the infiltration process. The resulting simulation and experiment values are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: a) In-plane temperature distribution at 6583 s simulation time, b-f) Comparison of simulation (Abaqus/CCA [5]) and experiment at the different positions

The experiment did not show a 1D behavior. The resin rich area at the inlet led to an early exothermic temperature peak and hence triggered further exothermic reactions in the adjacent laminate. Thus a side to side cure with a time delay of approximately 380 s in-between laminate center plane temperature peaks was superimposed on the outside to inside cure attributed to the process setup with the heat introduction at the top and bottom side. Figure 4 a) shows this side to side cure at the time $t=6583$ s: when the peak temperature at position 12 of 172.2 °C is reached, temperature at position 9 was as low as 126 °C and ascended with further experiment progress to a peak of 165 °C at the time $t=7076$ s.

A reasonable fit was found for the timing and peak temperature between experimental and simulation results utilizing the mapped initial temperature and temperature boundary conditions on top and bottom only. Consistently all simulation results showed a premature peak approximately 160 s ahead of schedule compared to the experiment. A potential reason is a deviation between the literature values for the thermal properties for the fiber gathered from literature and their actual properties. Especially the fiber material properties in transverse direction are often estimated due to lack of experimental measurement methods. Peak temperature comparison of simulation and experiment were -0.1 °C/ -0.3 °C/ -8.1 °C/ -2.6 °C/ -3.6 °C at the positions Center/ Pos.8/ Pos.9/ Pos.12/ Pos.13, thus showed good agreement at all locations but for node 9. The root cause of the relatively big deviation at node 9 is suspected to be the fiber volume fraction assumed being too low, which would result in higher temperature peaks.

2.4 Tool Material

The quasi-isotropically laid up CFRP tool was manufactured with Araldite LY86151 / TR30S and a target fiber volume fraction of 56 %. The resin system was chosen to have a significantly higher glass transition temperature than the curing temperature of the resin to ensure shape stability of the tool at cure temperature of the part. All relevant properties for thermal analysis but the in-plane conductivity $k_{in-plane}$ were measured via DSC and NanoFlash™. Heat capacity was measured at six equidistant temperature levels from 50 °C to 150 °C. Temperature conductivity was measured with three specimens at five equidistant temperature levels from 20 °C to 140 °C. The in-plane heat conductivity $k_{in-plane}$ of the quasi-isotropic laminate was calculated from literature values of fiber and matrix utilizing classical laminate theory (CLT) [12]. The resulting values are shown in Table 2. The

investigated temperatures were significantly lower than the glass transition temperature of the tooling resin at approximately 200 °C. Thus the experiments were all conducted in the glassy state and heat capacity and conductivity showed close to linear behavior with temperature. Hence it was feasible to interpolate missing values in-between measurement data. The resulting description of the thermal material behavior is shown Table 2.

Temperature [°C]	ρ [kg/m ³]	c_p [J/kg/°C]	$k_{\text{transverse}}$ [W/m/°C]	$k_{\text{in-plane}}$ [W/m/°C]
20	1470	875	0.469	2.33
50	-	1075	0.547	2.50
80	-	1193	0.582	2.65
110	-	1300	0.613	2.80
140	-	1410	0.630	2.93

Table 2: Thermal tool properties

3 MODELLING AN IN SITU HEATED CFRP TOOL

3.1 Model requirements

An accurate thermochemical simulation in terms of degree of cure distribution, cure rate and transient temperature requires an adequate modelling of the heating source for the RTM setup. In Figure 5, a 2D sketch of the in situ heated CFRP tool is given. The resistive heating plane is allocated in the center plane of the tooling shell and electrically isolated from the tool itself. According to the manufacturer a constant energy introduction over the area is ensured. The amount of energy introduced is controlled by a control loop consisting of a thermocouple located in the heating plane and an exterior feedback system. The system controls the power introduction in such a way that the target temperature at the thermocouple location is enforced. Neglecting in-plane effects, 1D stationary energy balance at the thermocouple gives

$$\dot{Q}_{\text{heating area}} = \dot{Q}_{\text{convection}} + \dot{Q}_{\text{part}} \quad (3)$$

$$\dot{Q}_{\text{heating area}} < 0 \Rightarrow \dot{Q}_{\text{heating area}} = 0. \quad (4)$$

Equation 4 acknowledges the fact that resistive heating elements cannot be used for cooling. In case of apparent exothermic reactions, the control loop will reduce the introduced energy to zero if the right hand side of Equation 3 is negative.

Figure 5: Sketch of an in situ heated CFRP tool

A stationary investigation of Section A in Figure 5 shows that although this heating system is highly adaptable if many heating patches are used, a uniform in-plane temperature distribution is not necessarily given within one heating patch: Even if the part heat flow \dot{Q}_{part} is independent of the location, a temperature gradient towards the left side of Section A is expected. Given that the left side of Section A is also subject to the heat flows $\dot{Q}_{\text{convection}}$ and/or \dot{Q}_{part} but does not contain internal energy introduction, the left side will reach lower temperatures than Section A. Due to in-plane heat conduction Section A will reach lower temperatures than the thermocouple placed more centrally. As

demonstrated with this example, the introduced energy $\dot{Q}_{heating\ area}$ enforces target temperature at the thermocouple, but not in the whole heating area due to in-plane heat conduction and non-uniform heat flow into the part \dot{Q}_{part} . Low in-plane conductivity of CFRP boosts this effect.

Consequently the requirements on the cure simulation boundary conditions are:

1. Modelling of the tool laminate is required, because low CFRP conductivities are suspected to have a significant effect on the part surface temperatures.
2. Heat introduction in one patch is constant within the heating area surface, but transient.
3. The amount of heat introduced over time is controlled in such way, that the location of the thermocouple reaches target temperature.
4. If the temperature at the location of the thermocouple exceeds target temperature, the heat introduction is set to zero.

Whereas implementation of the first condition is straight forward, the remaining requirements pose a challenge in FEA. Linear combinations of Dirichlet and Neumann boundary conditions are typically used to apply a temperature dependent heat flow such as convection. Those heat flow boundary conditions are calculated by weighting a temperature difference between the considered element and a defined temperature. In the present case this cannot be utilized as the heat flow introduced in the whole heating area is dependent on the temperature of only one point in the domain, irrespective of the element considered. Hence a specifically designed control mechanism had to be introduced.

3.2 Implementation

In general most control mechanism applied in the industry use a linear time invariant (LTI) control loop feedback such as a proportional-integral-derivative controller (PID controller). This could be introduced within FE to calculate the heat flow boundary condition via additional user subroutines. The control system would be defined by the geometry and the assigned material properties. However, in curing simulation the material properties change, hence the control system changes over time. The prerequisite of the application of LTI control mechanisms is not given as the system response is time variant, e.g. the system will respond differently precure, during cure and postcure. Thus another solution was developed which is able to cope with the time variant system at hand.

The general idea of the method developed was the utilization of the conservation of energy law in the application of a temperature boundary condition on a single node: To satisfy this law the system, in the present case the FE-Solver, needs to add or subtract energy onto the node. A node with an applied boundary condition can therefore be seen as a heat source or sink, dependent on the surrounding nodal temperatures. For a more convenient handling, the energy is calculated into power to gain an independency of the time increment length within the FE-Analysis. This power is given as the reaction flux (RFL) within Abaqus thermal analysis nodal solving output. It is mesh-dependent, as the attributed thermal mass and thus the attributed volume of a node depends on the element size and drives the nodal heat flux balances.

The RFL is tracked within an FE analysis in the control strategy implemented for the setup at hand. Mesh dependency is negated with a nodal factor m and the resulting power per area is calculated and applied on the whole domain of the heating patch. Thus the calculated heat flux boundary condition is a result of the RFL. The RFL is only accessible at the end of the increment, because it is a product of the temperature field solved for. The heat flux boundary condition has to be defined before the LES is solved for, therefore the RFL of the previous increment has to be used as an input for calculation of the power introduction per area in the next increment. Hence the calculated heat flux boundary conditions presents an approximation, but the effect is negligible if the time increments chosen are small enough. If the temperature boundary condition is equal to the target temperature cycle, the introduced power equals the amount of power needed to reach target temperature at the position of the considered node, henceforth called sensor node. Compensating mesh influence by the factor m , the resulting heat flux per area Δp which is required in the heat patch domain to reach target temperature in the time step i at the sensor node is described by

$$\Delta p^i = m \cdot RFL^i \approx m \cdot RFL^{i-1}. \quad (5)$$

Although equation 5 gives an accurate prediction on the necessary power per area in theory, direct

application led to very small time steps and oscillating behavior around the target value in transient FEA application even though additional extrapolation and/or damping terms were introduced. The reasons are the reactive nature and the delay of one time step in combination with big changes in the RFL.

Further development was made considering not only the nature of RFL, but also the whole control mechanism with regard to the FE-sequence: If a heat flux boundary condition is applied on a domain containing the sensor node, the sensor node is subject to two sequential different energy introductions: First the heat flux boundary condition is applied, and secondly the RFL is iterated in such way that target temperature is reached. Hence, the RFL resembles the additional power required besides the heat flux boundary condition.

$$p^i = p^{i-1} + \Delta p^i \quad (6)$$

With the starting condition

$$p^1 = 0 \quad (7)$$

Insertion and simplification of Equation 5, 6 and 7 and introduction of an additional damping constant results in the mathematical description of the control algorithm:

$$p^i \approx D \cdot m \cdot \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} RFL^j, \quad i > 1 \quad (8)$$

The damping constant D is set between 0 and 1 and defines the number of time steps required until convergence is reached. With the application of Equation 8, the RFL resembles only the necessary power introduction change from the previous step. The majority of necessary energy introduction due to heat-up and convection is accounted for in the initial time steps of the simulation. The resulting power introduction change from one time step to the next is low compared to overall power introduction. Hence Equation 8 leads to a non-problematic asymptotic behavior if the predominantly applied linear temperature ramps and holds are used. The necessary power introduction change during cure may be high if high cure rates are reached, but in this case the time steps are required to be low due to cure simulation accuracy requirements, which again leads to smaller necessary changes in the power introduction and the applicability of Equation 8.

For a successful implementation of the developed control algorithm, an addition to the FE model had to be made to satisfy the fourth requirement mentioned in the previous section. If the sensor node is located within the tool middle plane and a temperature boundary condition is applied, the node may act as a heat sink if an exothermic reaction occurs. However, the self-heated CFRP tools are only able to cool down due to convection, thus heat sinks within the heating plane are not acceptable in an accurate curing simulation. In the specific time step, when the sensor node temperature would exceed target temperature, the temperature boundary condition has to be eliminated and the additional degree of freedom has to be solved for. Aiming at general applicability, an adaptive solution was sought to account for different simulation models. However, temperature boundary condition cannot be switched-off adaptively, as the number of degree of freedoms and hence the size of the solved LES changes.

If the FE solver cannot be influenced directly in an adaptive way the only other option is the change of the simulation model: The temperature boundary condition was applied on a reference node outside the tool domain, and a multi-point constraint (MPC) was established to connect the reference node and the sensor node at the location of the thermocouple. The MPC was set up to enforce temperature equality between the reference node and the sensor node. Finally an addition to the control mechanism was made: If the introduced heat flux over the area resembles cooling and becomes negative, the MPC is switched off and the introduced heat flux is set to zero. Thus the sensor node in the heating domain can be iterated freely. If sensor node temperature is lower than target temperature, the MPC and thus the control mechanism is switched on again.

The developed control algorithm is a direct FE-representation of the in situ self-heated CFRP tool. It satisfies all requirements of the previous section.

4 VALIDATION OF THE IN SITU HEAT PATCH IMPLEMENTATION

The numerical validation of the control algorithm was made by simulation of three test cases: CFRP tool compensating convection during an isothermal hold, CFRP tool heating of thermal masses, and CFRP tool used to heat up curing laminates subject to exothermic reactions. All three scenarios are relevant during the heat up, isothermal hold and cure of a thick CFRP laminate with the CFRP-tool. During heat up the required energy introduction is dominated by the thermal masses of tool and part, during curing it is dominated by the occurring exothermic reaction, post-cure cool down is dominated by convection. The simulation setup is depicted in Figure 6, the dimensions are given in mm.

Figure 6: Validation model setup

The validation model consisted of 30 mm curing laminate and 8 mm cured tool CFRP laminate on the top and bottom side. A heat transfer coefficient of 22 W/m²/°C and 10 W/m²/°C was applied at the top and bottom side to account for two different convection coefficients, the four remaining sides were modeled adiabatic. The heating plane was located in the middle-plane of the tool laminate and the control strategy was applied with reference points outside the domain and the sensor node located at position A in Figure 6. The initial temperature was set at 80°C, followed by a temperature ramp of 1.5 °C/min up to 120 °C and an 8400 s hold at that temperature.

Figure 7 shows the heating plane temperatures of a node located at Position B. It is divided into the three scenarios mentioned above. Whereas a clear division between scenarios “Heat-up” and “Hold during cure” is possible, the later division between “Hold during cure” and “Convective cold-down and hold” is only an approximation as chemical reaction governed by diffusion processes also takes place in the last process scenario. This division is set at the time where the remaining chemical reaction results in negligible impact on the temperatures.

The first scenario, heat-up from 80 °C to 120 °C showed a close correlation between target temperatures and controlled heating area temperature. No estimation terms were introduced to negate the time delay of one time increment in the control algorithm, therefore a small overshoot of 1.5°C at the transition from heat up to cure and convection was observed. The reason was a significant drop in necessary introduced energy once the hold stage was reached. Within the cure stage, the control strategy aims for target temperature with similar success at first, after 2750 s the exothermic temperature overshoot led to a discrepancy between target temperature and heat area temperature. This was expected, because no heating area cooling effects take place within the tool. Hence, the control strategy is required to not influence the temperature field when sensor node temperatures are above target temperature. The curing of the laminate progressed from the outside surfaces towards the middle because of low out of plane heat conductivity common in CFRP laminates. The temperatures in the center of the laminate started rising above target temperature at approximately 2350 s simulation time,

maximum temperature of 178 °C was reached at 3150 s. Shortly after this time at approximately 3600 s the laminate was almost fully cured, only small amounts of additional reaction energy were released and temperature development in the heating plane was dominated by convection. A low temperature undershoot similar in duration and amplitude to the previous overshoot was observed as soon as the heating plane temperature of the top and bottom side reached target temperature again. From this point on, the compensation of convection is enforced by the control algorithm with almost no discrepancy between target temperature and actual heating plane temperature.

Figure 7: Validation of the implemented heating algorithm

All three relevant application scenarios, heat-up, exothermic reaction and convective cool-down with a temperature hold were controlled by the algorithm with good success. In the transition from one scenario to the next, temperature over- or undershoots lower than 3 °C were detected. The amount of time until the control algorithm successfully corrects the introduced power depends on the time step length. The algorithm needed five time steps to control the introduced power in such way that a temperature discrepancy lower than 1°C between target and heating plane temperature was reached. No influence of the different convection coefficients and hence the total amount of introduced energy required on the convergence of the algorithm was observed.

5 SUMMARY

An RTM tool made of steel or aluminum supports to gain uniform surface temperature distribution during processing of CFRP parts due to its high thermal mass and heat conductivity. In case of CFRP RTM tool, achievement of a uniform in-plane temperature distribution is challenging given that the thermal conductivities are reduced by at least one magnitude compared to metal alloys. This may lead to an enhanced risk of exothermic temperature overshoot, but it is also potentially beneficial in the production of thick CFRP parts with varying cross sections, where diverse temperature fields in different part sections may lead to a more homogeneous cure. The novel self-heated CFRP RTM tool made by Qpoint targets this potential. Within the present paper, a simulation strategy was implemented and validated in the Abaqus/CCA FE environment to enable accurate simulation of the cure of parts manufactured within the self-heated CFRP tool.

A control strategy was developed, which is capable of controlling the introduced heating power in such way, that a desired temperature at a previously defined point in the heating area is reached. The in situ heating patches are not able to cool the laminate internally, which is accounted for in the control strategy. Thus, a factually equivalent boundary condition to the physical behavior of in situ heating system of CFRP tools was developed.

The resin system Cytec CYCOM 823-1 RTM has been characterized regarding cure kinetics, heat capacity and conductivity. In order to account for the cure of thick laminates, a wide range of

temperatures above and below the cure temperature given by the manufacturer were investigated and the material models were fitted accordingly. Validation of the material characterization on a 31 mm CFRP coupon showed a good fit between simulation and experiment even during significant exothermic temperature overshoots.

Finally the implemented control strategy was validated by a cure simulation of a 30 mm laminate sandwiched in-between in situ heated CFRP plates. CFRP tool properties were estimated with a combination of experimental and literature values. The implemented control strategy showed the capability of controlling the introduced heating power in such a way, that all requirements for an accurate representation of an in situ heated CFRP plate are reached during the three cure cycle phases heat-up, hold and cool-down.

The present work represents the foundation for the simulation of an RTM cure process with the new in situ heated CFRP tool. Future work will contain investigations on a prototype part with an industrially relevant level of geometric complexity where application of the heating system to ensure optimal temperature development within the part will be demonstrated.

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